

Open Access availability and Publication distribution of Social Science and Humanities Journals in OpenCitations Meta

Version 4

Description

This DMP is created to address to Research Question number one according to the course "[Open Science](#)" at the UNIBO. The purpose of the data collection and generation is to assess the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities journals' citation data coverage in OpenCitation databases and investigate how many of these are Open Access. The data will be used to analyze which countries and disciplines hold the most publications and journals. This information is essential to achieving the project's objectives of understanding the openness of Social Science and Humanities publications and promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration and wider dissemination of knowledge.

Funder

University of Bologna

Grant

OpenScience

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Bologna

Datasets

Title: SSH_OA_Publications_in_OCMeta

Template: Horizon 2020

The dataset contains the results of our research on OpenCitationMeta's coverage of Social Science and Humanities publications and their Open Access availability. This research is being carried out in the context of the Open Science course of Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge MA degree at University of Bologna.

The purpose of the dataset is to be able to easily access and retrieve, as well as visualize the outcome of our research project.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To combine with other data

The purpose of our data collection/generation is to obtain information about the current state of SSH citations metadata in OpenCitations Meta database. OCMeta database collects metadata about citations, very important information about articles and their citation network are therefore available even if those publications are not open access. Understanding what is the coverage of SSH journals and how many of these are Open Access, can give meaningful insights for future development of OCMeta database and for Open Access advocacy and implementation.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- reference or canonical (e.g.

- static
- peer-reviewed data sets
- likely published or curated
- such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

Data are reused from

- ERIH-PLUS Journals Dataset (The list is open and free to use, they only ask that you use the official name, ERIH PLUS, when referring to the data source)
- OpenCitations Meta (Creative Commons public domain dedication, [CC0](#))
- DOAJ ([licenses](#))

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Discipline specific formats

1. CSV

2. JSON

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Social Science and Humanities researchers, Open Science experts

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite standard

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

The metadata will be available on Zenodo

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

We can upload our metadata in Zenodo repository, which has long standing and solid user base, although it is not certified yet.

Might also check out: [OAI-PMH](#)

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

<https://github.com/open-sci/2022-2023-playarists-code/blob/main/README.md>

self-defined

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

[Semantic Versioning](#)

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

DOIs and URIs

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

a. DOI

b. URI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.16 Provide information about used standardised formats

a. <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

JSON

b. <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc4180>

CSV

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

Other

Zenodo

also in a public repository on github (github repo can also be published in Zenodo).

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

Zenodo stores reaserch data safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make thedescribed data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 1.0 Generic (CC BY 1.0)

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

There will be a documentation on how to reuse them. An article will also explain how the data have been obtained and how to interpret them

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Less than 2 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

Data management is entrusted to all three project members, however, a data manager has been identified to supervise the management of the data.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Sebastiano Giacomini (orcid:0009-0007-7813-0939)

Data manager, data model design and quality assurance

b. Maddalena Ghiotto (orcid:0009-0009-1309-6340)

RDF metadata description

c. Seyedali Ghasempouri (orcid:0000-0003-3446-1115)

Documentation written on purpose and reuse of data

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other
- Personal Archive

Github, Zenodo

The final dataset will be available both in a dedicated Github repository and in Zenodo, along with comprehensive documentation to simplify data reuse.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

We aim to preserve our data in a secure environment even after the end of the project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Data management software](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

A Software for the analysis and creation of our data. In particular, this Python software is intended to filter, fetch, and process the data provided by ERIH-PLUS, OpenCitations Meta, and DOAJ, in order to make it available and reusable for some meaningful analysis.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

This software should filter data and return some meaningful information to answer our research question.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)
- Other

The software has been created according to the available input data and taking in consideration the desired outputs.

Python programming language files.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Other

Python code.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

This software could help researchers and research communities in filtering and comparing collected data according to their purposes. At the same time, decision makers could take advantage of the results of the software and the software itself to obtain different results.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes metadata will be published on Zenodo, which is OAI-PMH compliant

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

It will be used a simple and clear versioning scheme like Semantic Versioning (SemVer). SemVer uses a three-part version number: MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH, e.g., 1.2.3.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Beside zenodo, we could publish the software also in Software Heritage repository.

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.14 Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://github.com/codemeta/codemeta>

Zenodo, figshare

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

[Open source tools for software](#)

Visual Studio Code

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

Other

GitHub

Github, Zenodo

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.7 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the data

Download free of charge from repository

3.1.2.8 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the data.

No special tool is needed.

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

after publication

A notebook providing guidelines on how to use the software and an article introducing how the outputs should be interpreted.

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

end of project

As soon as the software is completed and quality checked

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

CC BY 1.0

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

Software quality checklist

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification

We will create synthetic data to test the software functioning, given the complexity and size of the datasets.

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

usage guidelines in the github repository.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Less than 2 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure

- Use of institution infrastructure

no cost is planned

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

All members of the research group (the authors of the DMP)

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Maddalena Ghiotto (orcid:0009-0009-1309-6340)

Responsible for FAIR software implementation and publication

b. Sebastiano Giacomini (orcid:0009-0007-7813-0939)

Responsible for FAIR software implementation and publication

c. Seyedali Ghasempouri (orcid:0000-0003-3446-1115)

Responsible for FAIR software implementation and publication

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Other

GitHub, Zenodo

- Make the data FAIR: we will ensure that the data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR).
- Clear licensing: we will apply a clear and permissive license to your data that specifies the terms of use and any restrictions. Open licenses like Creative Commons licenses (e.g., CC0) encourage data reuse by making it easy for others to understand their rights and responsibilities when using the data.
- Comprehensive documentation: we will provide thorough documentation and metadata for our data, describing the content, context, and any necessary processing steps.
- Monitor data reuse: We will monitor the reuse of the data and track metrics such as citation counts, downloads.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

to select a repository, we consider factors such as:

- Long-term preservation and stability
- Adherence to the FAIR principles
- Reputation and trustworthiness
- Support for relevant data formats and metadata standards
- Licensing options and data access controls
- Integration with other research infrastructure (e.g., ORCID, DOI registration)
- Cost and funding requirements

We use general-purpose repositories, like Zenodo, and GitHub that accept data from multiple disciplines. We use GitHub for storing and sharing certain types of data, particularly source code, documentation, and small datasets.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Yes

The primary ethical and legal issues that may impact data sharing are related to data protection, intellectual property, and open access restrictions, since not all publications or journals indexed in ERIH-PLUS are open access. However, considering that our project focuses on analyzing metadata and aggregated data from various public sources (ERIH-PLUS, OpenCitations Meta, and DOAJ), rather than personal or sensitive information about individuals the risks are relatively low.

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

we have these concerns:

Data version control: Use version control systems (e.g., Git)

Data validation and quality control: Implement data validation and quality control procedures to ensure that our data is accurate and consistent. This may involve checking for missing or inconsistent data, verifying data accuracy, and documenting any known data quality issues.

Data organization and standardization: Organize our data using standard file formats, naming conventions, and directory structures. This will make it easier for others to access and use our data.

7.1.2 Please provide links to documentation on these other procedures

- Data documentation: The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI): <https://ddialliance.org/>
- Data organization and standardization: <https://datacarpentry.org/spreadsheet-ecology-lesson/02-common-mistakes/index.html>

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